

Optimisation of Code_Saturne for Petascale Simulations

^aC. Moulinec, A.G. Sunderland¹

^bP. Kabelikova, A. Ronovsky, V. Vondrak²

^cA. Turk, C. Aykanat³

^dC. Theodosiou⁴

a Computational Science and Engineering Department, STFC Daresbury Laboratory, United Kingdom

b Department of Applied Mathematics, VSB-Technical University of Ostrava, 17. listopadu 15, 708 33 Ostrava, Czech Republic

c Department of Computer Engineering, Bilkent University, 06800 Bilkent Ankara, Turkey

d Scientific Computational Center, Aristotle University, 54 124 Thessaloniki, Greece

Abstract

Some of the optimisations required to prepare Code_Saturne for petascale simulations are presented in this white paper, along with the performance of the code. A mesh multiplication package based on parallel global refinement of hexahedral meshes has been developed for Code_Saturne to handle meshes containing billions[†] of cells and to efficiently exploit PRACE Tier-0 system capabilities. Several parallel partitioning tools have been tested and Code_Saturne performance has been assessed up to a 3.2 billion cell mesh. The parallel code is highly scalable and demonstrates good parallel speed-up at very high core counts, e.g. from 32,768 to 65,536 cores.

1. Introduction and Objectives of the Project

It is estimated that a mesh of about 15 billion cells (15B) would be required to simulate the flow in a full reactor of a power plant using Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD), and more specifically by using Large-Eddy Simulation (LES). Code_Saturne [1, 2] is a multi-purpose CFD software developed by EDF-R&D since 1997. It has been released as open source in 2007 and is now distributed under a GPL license. The code was originally designed for both industrial applications and research activities in several fields related to energy production, and has been selected as part of the PRACE benchmark suite for the engineering community, during both PRACE-PP and PRACE-IIP.

Code_Saturne is based upon a co-located finite volume approach that can handle three-dimensional meshes built with any type of cell (tetrahedral, hexahedral, prismatic, pyramidal, polyhedral) and with any type of grid structure

¹ Corresponding author. *E-mail address:* charles.moulinec@stfc.ac.uk

² Corresponding author. *E-mail address:* vit.vondrak@vsb.cz

³ Corresponding author. *E-mail address:* atat@cs.bilkent.edu.tr

⁴ Corresponding author. *E-mail address:* ctheo@grid.auth.gr

[†] This paper uses the *short scale* definition of a billion throughout, i.e. one billion is equal to one thousand million

(unstructured, block structured, hybrid). The code is able to simulate either incompressible or weakly compressible flows, with or without heat transfer, and has a variety of turbulence models.

The main algorithm used is Parallelised Multigrid Conjugate Gradient in the sparse linear solver stage of calculations for the pressure. In typical cases involving many thousands of time-steps, this stage dominates overall run-time. Work is in progress in a separate project to introduce OpenMP into the MPI multigrid solver, which will result in a hybrid MPI/OpenMP parallelisation once complete.

I/O performance is relevant for Code_Saturne, as the very large-scale simulations that the code undertakes require large amounts of input data and output data (e.g. for visualisation of results). Code_Saturne supports MPI-IO but a new parallel I/O approach has recently also been implemented in the code in the cases where MPI-IO is not available on the target machine. I/O is undertaken using a block distribution of data and collective operations on shared files. This is a similar approach to that used internally by MPI-IO.

The main bottleneck in CFD applied to complex geometries is the ability to generate large meshes and the time required for it. Alternative solutions exist, as for example, joining parts of a large mesh or splitting all the cells of an original mesh (also called mesh multiplication).

It is premature to aim at this stage for 15 billion cell meshes, but a 2 billion cell mesh has already been generated by a Code_Saturne joining procedure in 2011, the solver not being tested then due to a lack of allocated resources at that time. Therefore, the technical objectives of the current project are:-

- to generate more than 2 billion cell meshes,
- to test the Navier-Stokes solver for LES,
- to run Code_Saturne on 60,000+ cores.

Section 2 deals with the presentation of the test cases, Section 3 gives the list of the machines and compilers used for this work, Section 4 describes shortly the mesh generation strategy, Section 5 lists the various partitioning methods used and Section 6 describes the results, before concluding in Section 7.

2. Test Cases

The main test cases consist of Large-Eddy Simulations in a bundle of staggered-distributed tubes. The configuration corresponds to the one experimentally studied by Simonin and Barcouda [3, 4]. Figure 1(a) shows the elemental configuration containing a whole tube in its centre and four quarter of tubes in the corners. The elemental configuration contains about 13 million (13M) cells (the 2-D cross-section has got 100,040 cells and 128 layers are used in the third direction). Figure 1(b) shows a 2-D cross-section of a mesh containing 4x4 elemental configurations (note that, depending on the design, 15x15 or 17x17 tubes are used in the plants). The size of the meshes used in this work is given in Table 1.

Table 1. Size of the meshes used to assess Code_Saturne performance

Type of mesh	Number of Cells
Original Mesh	12,805,120
2*2 full tubes (51M)	51,220,480
4*4 full tubes (204M)	204,881,920
8*8 full tubes (816M)	819,527,680
16*16 full tubes (3.2B)	3,278,110,720

Fig 1 (a): Elemental cell containing one full tube. (b): Large bundle of tubes. Example of 4 x 4 tubes.

3. Machines and Compilers

Three machines are used for this work: JUGENE, CURIE and HECToR. The Intel compiler (version 12.1) is used on CURIE, the XL compiler (version 9.0) on JUGENE and the GNU compiler (version 4.6.2) on HECToR. Appropriate performance optimization flags are used in each case.

4. Mesh Generation

Generating large meshes for CFD is one of the main bottlenecks of CFD. Subsection 4.1 summarises the mesh joining procedure as it already exists in Code_Saturne and Subsection 4.2 briefly presents the mesh multiplication approach implemented in Code_Saturne by VSB within PRACE-IIP WP7.6.

4.1 Mesh Joining

Code_Saturne has been designed to load multiple meshes and join them together, whether those meshes are conforming or not [5]. This allows meshing of a geometry in separate pieces, and thus somewhat working around the limitations of serial meshing tools. This automatic joining step may now be done in parallel. The non-conforming interfaces are detected by an octree-based algorithm, and are joined together in a similar fashion to the way periodicity is treated in Code_Saturne. For instance, if two meshes have to be joined and if their common interface is non-conforming, the surface faces are subdivided according to their intersection so as to obtain conforming subfaces, which may be any type of simple polygon. Cells adjacent to those faces thus become general polyhedral cells, even if they were initially tetrahedral, prisms, or hexahedral cells. Periodicity is handled as an extension of mesh joining, by joining “ghost” copies of periodic faces, such that periodicity is intrinsic to the

geometry discretisation, and not just a boundary condition (i.e. periodic faces are true interior faces, not boundary faces).

4.2 Mesh Multiplication

Mesh multiplication is the process of taking an existing mesh and changing its size, i.e. number and/or shape of the cells to increase accuracy of the solution. In the limited time frame of this work around Code_Saturne, mesh multiplication of regular (hexahedral-based) meshes only is tackled, where a higher accuracy of solution is obtained by refining each cell of the mesh. A full description of the method can be found in [6] with results showing the method being able to generate a 4.3B cell mesh from an original mesh of 0.016M cells in only 28 seconds on CURIE. Although not fully implemented in the code to-date, a stand-alone version has been used successfully in conjunction with Code_Saturne and has yielded promising initial results. Mesh multiplication is potentially a very powerful tool for handling large and complex datasets in Code_Saturne.

5. Partitioning

Partitioning billion cell meshes needs to be undertaken in parallel as neither front-end machines nor cluster nodes have sufficient memory to perform this task serially. The parallel partitioner in Code_Saturne relies on a Space Filling Curve (SFC) algorithm based on the Morton approach, but other libraries might be used within Code_Saturne pre-processing stage, e.g. METIS 5.0, SCOTCH 5.1.12, ParMETIS 4.0.2 and PT-SCOTCH 5.1.12. Former tests conducted on JUGENE with a 107M mesh [2] concluded that PT-SCOTCH produces better partitionings for Code_Saturne than ParMETIS and SFC (Morton).

To prepare for the new generation of high-end machines comprising of many nodes with many cores per node, Bilkent University has developed a hierarchical mesh partitioner based on graph partitioning between nodes (based on ParMETIS) and a fast partitioning algorithm within each node of the machine. At this stage of development, this partitioning does not look as efficient as ParMETIS alone on the aforementioned 107M case and it is not considered here for further testing. More information can be found in the PRACE-1IP WP7.6 white paper [7]. SFC, ParMETIS and PT-SCOTCH are then used as partitioning tools in the following.

6. Results

The ultimate goal of this work is to assess the ability of Code_Saturne's Navier-Stokes solver to handle meshes of at least 2 billion cells and if possible compute on more than 60,000 cores. The two PRACE Tier-0 machines available within WP7.2, i.e. JUGENE and CURIE have diverse architectures, the first one with 4 cores per node and 2GB RAM available per node and the second one with 32 cores per node and 128GB RAM per node. Therefore CURIE appears the best target machine for this work, as about 4GB per MPI task are required to perform the mesh joining operation for the 3.2B case. Unfortunately, the size of the jobs to be run on CURIE is currently limited to a maximum of 2,048 processors, which prevents testing the code at scale. For these reasons, it has been decided to first compare Code_Saturne performance on JUGENE and CURIE, before running the largest simulations on HECToR, where runs of up to 65,536 cores can be undertaken.

Fig 2 (a): Comparative performance of Code_Saturne on JUGENE, CURIE and HECToR (Cray XE6) for the 51M case and the 204M case for JUGENE and HECToR. (b): CPU time per time step in seconds required by Code_Saturne for the 51M, 204M, 816M and 3.2B cases, when PT-SCOTCH, ParMETIS and SFC are used as partitioners.

Code_Saturne's performance is assessed on the three machines for the 51M and 204M cell mesh cases and results are presented in Figure 2 (a). A performance speed-up is observed in all the cases, even when going from 16,384 to 32,768 cores on JUGENE. This comparison also demonstrates Code_Saturne's portability on machines with various architectures, and compilers.

Figure 2(b) shows the performance for the 51M, 204M, 816M and 3.2B cell meshes on HECToR. Overall, best performance is usually achieved by PT-SCOTCH for the 51M, 204M and 816M case. To date only the SFC partitioning tool could be used for the 3.2B case. Code_Saturne was run on that case up to 65,536 cores and a speed-up was observed going from 32,768 to 65,536 cores.

7. Conclusions

This project on Code_Saturne has demonstrated that the code is ready to run on petascale machines, as shown by the speed-up observed going from 32,768 to 65,536 cores for a 3.2B cell mesh. The objectives of this project have been fulfilled, as 2B cell meshes had to be handled by the code and its performance has been assessed on 60,000+ cores. This work has also strongly benefited from two other projects carried out within PRACE-IIP WP7.6, the first one lead by VSB concerning mesh multiplication, and the second one by Bilkent University based on developing a hierarchical partitioning tool. Future work will involve testing the code on larger meshes, of up to 12-15B cell and assessing Code_Saturne scalability in the mixed mode MPI/OpenMP.

Acknowledgements

This work was financially supported by the PRACE project funded in part by the EU's 7th Framework Programme (FP7/2007-2013) under grant agreement no. RI-211528 and FP7-261557. The work is achieved using the PRACE Research Infrastructure resources [JUGENE, GERMANY and CURIE, FRANCE]. The author would also like to thank EPSRC for providing them CPU time on HECToR, Yvan Fournier from EDF R&D for his expertise and

constant support, and Juan Uribe from the University of Manchester for his help to run the code in turbulent mode.

References

1. F. Archambeau, N. Mechtoua and M. Sakiz, *Code_Saturne® : a Finite Volume Code for the Computation of Turbulent Incompressible Flows - Industrial Applications*. International Journal on Finite Volumes, Vol. 1, 2004.
2. Y. Fournier, J. Bonelle, C. Moulinec, Z. Shang, A.G. Sunderland and J.C. Uribe, *Developing Code_Saturne® for Computing at the Petascale*, Y. Fournier, J. Bonelle, C. Moulinec, Z. Shang, A.G. Sunderland, J.C. Uribe. Computers & Fluids Vol. 45, Issue 1, June 2011, pp. 103–108.
3. O. Simonin and M. Barcouda, *Measurements and prediction of turbulent flow entering a staggered tube bundle*, Fourth International Symposium on Applications of Laser Anemometry to Fluid Mechanics. Lisbon, Portugal, 1988.
4. O. Simonin and M. Barcouda, *Flow Through Staggered Tube Bundle*, <http://cfd.mace.manchester.ac.uk/ercoftac/> (Search for Title by Keywords), 1986.
5. Y. Fournier, J. Bonelle, P. Vezolle, C. Moulinec and A.G. Sunderland, *An Automatic Joining Mesh Approach for CFD to Reach 1B Cell Simulation*, Pareng, 2011.
6. P. Kabelikova, A. Ronovsky and V. Vondrak, *Parallel Mesh Multiplication for Code_Saturne*, White Paper PRACE-IIP WP7.6, 2011.
7. A. Turk, C. Moulinec, A.G. Sunderland, C. Aykanat, *Code_Saturne Optimisations in Preprocessing*, White Paper PRACE-IIP WP7.6, 2011.